

**Mixed Ligand Complexes of Cadmium(II) with
Reactive Methylene Compounds of Malona-
mic Acid Series and Tartaric Acid :
A Polarographic Study**

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THE use of polarographic data for the study of complexation is well known^{1,2}. Reactive methylene compounds³ have been found to be excellent starting materials for the synthesis of various types of chemotherapeutic and analytical reagents. Hence, it was thought worthwhile to undertake the present investigation which is expected to furnish knowledge about formation and stability of complexes of cadmium(II).

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical reagent grade and their stock solutions were prepared in conductivity water. Sodium potassium tartarate and sodium salts of *N*-(2-ethoxy)phenylmalonic acid (EPM) and *N*-(2-chloro)phenylmalonic acid (CPM) were the source of Tart²⁻, EPM⁻ and CPM⁻ respectively. KCl was used as a supporting electrolyte and also to maintain a constant ionic strength. The concentration of each depolariser was maintained constant at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Polarograms of the solutions were obtained by means of a Toshniwal CL 02A polarograph in conjunction with a Toshniwal PL50 polyflex galvanometer. Purified nitrogen gas was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. All the measurements were made at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. A saturated calomel electrode (S.C.E.) was used as a reference electrode. The d.m.e. had the following characteristics: $m = 2.38 \text{ mg s}^{-1}$, $t = 3.4 \text{ s}$, $m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.10 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/3}$ (in 2.0 M KCl, open circuit), $h_{\text{corr}} = 62.5 \text{ cm}$.

Results and Discussion

The polarographic reduction of Cd^{II} in Tart²⁻, EPM⁻, CPM⁻ separately were found to be reversible and diffusion-controlled. The slopes of linear plots of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs $E_{a.e.}$ were of the order of $32 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$.

Cd^{II} - Tart²⁻ system: A plot of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{Tart}^{2-}]$ is a straight line which shows the formation of single complex. The value of coordination number J comes out to be 2, using Lingane's method². The composition of complex is $[\text{Cd}(\text{Tart})_2]^{2-}$ and its stability constant is $\log \beta_2 = 2.84$.

Cd^{II} - EPM⁻ and Cd^{II} - CPM⁻ system: The plots of $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{EPM}]^-$ and $E_{1/2}$ vs $\log [\text{CPM}]^-$ were straight lines showing the formation of single

complex in each case. The value of coordination number J comes out to be 2 in both the cases. Therefore, the composition of the complexes formed were $[\text{Cd}(\text{EPM})_2]$ and $[\text{Cd}(\text{CPM})_2]$ with stability constants $\log \beta_2 = 6.897$ and $\log \beta_2 = 6.491$ respectively.

$\text{Cd}^{II} - \text{Tart}^{2-} - \text{EPM}^-$ and $\text{Cd}^{II} - \text{Tart}^{2-} - \text{CPM}^-$ mixed systems: In each case a single well-defined reversible and diffusion-controlled wave was obtained, and $E_{1/2}$ values were more negative than those obtained in the absence of EPM^- and CPM^- showing the formation of mixed ligand complexes. Schaap and McMasters method⁴ has been used to determine the composition and stability constants of mixed complexes (Table 1).

TABLE 1—COMPOSITION AND STABILITY CONSTANTS OF MIXED COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II} WITH Tart^{2-} AND $\text{EPM}^-/\text{CPM}^-$ ION

Temp. = $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$			
System	Composition	Stability constant β_{11}	Mixing constant $\log k_M$
$\text{Cd}^{II} - \text{Tart}^{2-} - \text{EPM}^-$	$[\text{Cd}(\text{Tart})\text{EPM}]^-$	6.50	1.646
$\text{Cd}^{II} - \text{Tart}^{2-} - \text{CPM}^-$	$[\text{Cd}(\text{Tart})\text{CPM}]^-$	6.20	1.530

A comparative study of both the systems shows that the mixed system $[\text{Cd}(\text{Tart})(\text{EMP})]^-$ is more stable than $[\text{Cd}(\text{Tart})(\text{CPM})]^-$ which is further proved by the larger positive log value of mixing constant (k_M) for the reactions.

The positive log k_M values in both the cases also indicate the stability of mixed complexes over the simple complexes.

References

1. H. L. NIGAM, B. K. PANDEYA and V. S. VERMA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1990, **66**, 541; D. G. DHULRY and V. G. DONGRE, *Indian, J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1981, **20**, 208; W. U. MALIK and M. ASLAM, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **47**, 996; D. D. DEYFORD and D. D. HUME, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 5321; J. N. GAUR, M. M. PALRECHA, *Talanta*, 1968, **15**, 583; J. N. GAUR, A. K. MAHESWARI and D. S. JAIN, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1975, **37**, 805; D. A. GOVANNI and S. GIUSEPPA, *Ann. Chim. (Rome)*, 1964, **54**, 424; NOZAKI, TORU, KADOWAKI, MOTONORI, SAGAWA, DAIZIRO, ORITA and KUNITAKA, *Nippon Kagaku Zasshi*, 1970, **91**, 64.
2. J. J. LINGANE, *Chem. Rev.*, 1941, **29**, 1.
3. P. I. ITTYERAH and K. C. PANDYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **30**, 717; O. P. SINGHAL and P. I. ITTYERAH, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 448; D. S. SETH, B. C. BANERJI and P. I. ITTYERAH, *Agra Univ. J. Res. (Sci.)*, 1980, **29**, 27.
4. W. B. SCHAAP and D. L. MCMASTERS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **83**, 4699.